

EVIDENCE-BASED
TOXICOLOGY

Evaluation Report (Report 2) for **TEBT-2026-0002**

Submission Information Table

Submission Title	An AOP network of Neural Tube Defects
Submission Reference	TEBT-2026-0002.R0
Handling Editor	Paul Whaley 0000-0003-4021-0785 ▾
Editor Declaration of Interests	I am on the Stakeholder Advisory Board of ONTOX, an EU-funded research consortium of which the submitting authors are part. I previously handled and did not accept a different ONTOX-related manuscript (Verhoeven et al. 2025).
Number of Reviewers	1 editor + 2 peer-reviewers
Submission Type	Research Article ▾
Preregistration Category	N/A (Not Applicable) ▾ (explanation)
Preprint DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18757295
Report Number	2 ▾
Evaluation Stage	Peer-Review ▾
Evaluation Date	31 May 2026
Use of AI in evaluation	Microsoft Copilot was used by the handling editor to support cross-checking of the manuscript with disciplinary norms for reporting the development of AOPs. DataSeer.ai was used to check the consistency of the data availability statements in the manuscript with journal policies.

	Prophy.ai was used to identify suitable peer-reviewers for the manuscript.
Recommendation	Revise ▾

Summary of article and editor recommendations

This manuscript presents a comprehensive effort to derive from the literature a putative AOP network for neural tube defects (NTDs), with three sub-networks showing the role in NTDs of Wnt/PCP signalling, Grhl transcription, and Rho GTPases and EphA/ephrinA signalling.

Qualitative, weighted AOP networks such as the ones presented in the manuscript are an important step in the development of formal, quantitative AOPs, a broader process that benefits from the peer-review and publication of intermediary research products such as this.

During triage, the editor determined that the manuscript is complete enough to be ready for peer-review, although limitations were identified in the reporting of the literature search and screening methods, a lack of detail around the methods for interpreting the collected data into the AOP networks, and how the manuscript is so heavily dependent on visualisations for communicating its results.

The reviewers also commented on how the methods for the study do not fully explain how the results were derived and suggested improvements to the visualisations and general communication of results. Questions were also raised about choices for, and lack of, MIEs in the AOP networks.

That said, the reviewers were very positive about the paper and saw no fundamental obstacles to publication, just a need for revisions for clarity (although these revisions will be quite substantial).

Seriousness of issues identified with the reported work	The issues raised are important, as current gaps in the methods make it difficult for the reader to understand how the results were generated; and the way the results are presented do not make it clear enough what the results in fact are.
Potential additional work to overcome issues	The revisions requested are quite comprehensive and seem substantial in terms of time commitment, but they are not fundamental - no additional analysis is being requested, only clarification.
Acceptability of characterising limitations instead of further developing the reported work	This is unlikely, as the issue is not with the results of the research but with the clarity of the methods for deriving and presenting the results.

Checklist of minimum required information

Y = Yes, provided | R = Revisions, additions, or changes recommended | X = Not needed or not applicable

#	Status	Item checked
1	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	Preprint, relevant revision materials, and supplemental material available on Zenodo
2	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	Full name, affiliations, and ORCIDs (if available) of each author are present
3	<input type="radio"/>	Correct institutional co-authorship + email to EiC if official publication of EBTC
4	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	Structured abstract has been provided
5	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	Author contributions in the form of a CRediT statement have been given
6	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	Complete funding details are given, or “no funding” is declared
7	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	Informative disclosure of interests for all authors has been provided or disclosure declined
8	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	3rd-party data and program code are fully cited, if relevant (TOP 1, level 3)
9	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	Data and code availability is stated and links to both are functional (DAS templates)
10	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	One or more appropriate reporting checklists for submission type have been completed
11	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	Supplemental materials have plain English file names
12	<input type="radio"/>	For Registered Reports submissions, preregistration level clearly indicated

Comments about minimum required information

Key: Numbered according to the checklist items above, e.g. #5 would be a comment relating to declaration of author contributions

#4. Please provide a structured abstract, as it seems appropriate for this type of submission. I also note that about half the abstract introduces the concepts of AOPs and neural tube defects. When revising, I would suggest focusing on summarising the objective, methods, and results, to provide a concise summary of the content of the manuscript rather than the issues the manuscript is intended to address.

#7. The authors have not completed disclosure of interest forms. I am not sure how there could be a conflict of interest in relation to a manuscript such as this, but for formality’s sake it would be helpful if the authors could [complete the forms](#).

#10. I am not aware of any explicit reporting checklists for the development and reporting of AOPs. If the authors are aware of any appropriate checklist, or used one when developing their

AOP networks, please could they mention it. Likewise, if they are following any guidance, that should also be mentioned. For the literature search, appropriate checklists do exist, and I suggest the authors refer to PRISMA-S ([Rethlefsen et al. 2021](#)) for complete reporting of their search methodology.

Additional note: The authors did not use one of our cover letter templates (recommended option: single stage submissions). This is not a critical issue for this submission, as the authors included almost all the information we would ordinarily request, but the authors should be aware of these templates for future reference.

Reviewer Comments

Note about reviewer comments: Reviewer comments have been aggregated into the structured feedback below by the handling editor. Comments may have been edited for constructiveness or continuity, or annotated to indicate how the authors may consider responding. Comments are numbered for ease of reference.

1. General feedback

Editor's summary of reviewer comments and suggestions for responding

In their confidential comments to me, one of the reviewers felt more work should be done to outline a clear list of putative MIEs, particularly in view of the authors' discussion of how QSAR models can be trained to predict the ability of a chemical to activate MIEs based on MIE data.

I don't know the implications of this comment for the amount of work required to revise the manuscript: if it is clarification, then it is of a piece of many of the other comments; if it requires additional analysis, the authors should decide their capacity to do this and make clear any limitations this imposes on the manuscript and what future work needs to be done to address these.

Reviewer comments

Reviewer 1

1. First, I should note that although I am quite familiar with AOP development, I am not a subject matter expert in neural tube development. Consequently, I am unable to evaluate the specific biological aspects described in this study.

2. The authors present a proposed AOP network for neural tube defects, constructed based on a literature review focused on neural tube closure and its associated pathologies. The network comprises four subnetworks: disruption of Wnt/PCP signaling, aberrant morphogen gradients, altered Grhl activity, and dysregulated Rho/GTPase and EphA/ephrinA signaling. It is important to note that the network is putative in nature and was not developed according to the OECD AOP program guidance. Nevertheless, this work represents a valuable initial step towards the development of a robust and actionable AOP that could serve, once fully developed, as a useful framework for the interpretation of mechanistic data and the development of new approach methodologies.
3. Overall, the study is conceptually sound and generally well executed; however, the methods and results sections currently lack sufficient detail/clarity. The methods section would benefit from additional information to improve replicability, and the results section would be strengthened by clearer figures and more transparent reporting of findings (see specific comments below). Ultimately, as the authors acknowledge, this provisional AOP network will require comprehensive development and review under OECD guidance in order to support broader operational use.

Reviewer 2

4. Thank you for compiling and submitting your research to Evidence-Based Toxicology. The research is well written and contains a lot of mechanistic knowledge which will be of interest and use to other researchers within the domain. I have attached a document containing a list of suggestions and requested changes. The majority of these are minor.
5. The most pressing concern with the manuscript (that I would like to be addressed before publication) relates to the coverage of MIEs driving each pathway within the network. I would like the authors to consider the MIEs described within each of the relevant sections of the manuscript to ensure that the MIEs fit the concept of biological entities that are perturbed by a stressor. I would also like the authors to more clearly represent how these MIEs link into the AOP network (i.e. which KEs do each of the MIEs potentially perturb). I think without these clarifications the utility of the AOP network will be greatly limited. This is even highlighted in the discussion section of the manuscript, where the authors state how QSAR models can be trained to predict MIEs and thus

improve animal free risk assessments.

6. Having said the above, I found the manuscript very interesting and informative, and I am looking forward to seeing it published in this journal.

2. Are the research questions or knowledge goals clear, important, and sufficiently contextualised?

Reviewer comments

Reviewer 2

7. As it is a complex process, a figure representing neural tube closure could be beneficial for readers. The figure could incorporate all details outlined in lines 50-58 of pg1. e.g. a representation of neural tube closure and a visual representation of how environmental, nutritional and genetic factors can impair NTC and lead to the various NTDs. This change is not essential, but would improve the reader's experience.
8. The sentence spanning lines 5-11 of pg2 states that various in vivo test guidelines “remain the primary tools”. It is not 100% clear what these remain the primary tools for. Could you be more explicit here please? I believe the sentence is suggesting that these in vivo studies remain the primary method of elucidating the mechanisms driving neural tube defects. If I am correct, could you outline how these animal studies allow for interpretation of the mechanisms driving NTDs? If I have interpreted this incorrectly then consider changing the statement “remain the primary tools” to something along the lines of “allow for the identification of compounds which can cause NTDs”
9. Lines 22-23 of pg2, It should be commented on that these AOPs are not complete, perhaps stating “There are currently four draft AOPs available.....”

3. Is the theoretical approach being applied by the authors a logical, rational, and/or plausible approach for achieving their research goals?

Reviewer comments

Reviewer 2

10. Lines 30-31 of pg3. Your introduction states that NTC is well conserved in mammals. I am curious as to why you have included non-mammalian species such as zebrafish and xenopus in your species search. Please could you add a sentence to justify/explain the selection. Is the process of NTC thought to be conserved here too, or are these labels to filter out irrelevant studies?
11. lines 33-34 of pg3. Why were only the biological levels of molecular and tissue considered? Presumably it is because the gross malformations and organ outcomes are already well known, but please add a statement to clarify.

4. Is the methodology and/or analysis pipeline sound (including, if relevant, appropriate characterisation of its statistical power)?

Reviewer comments

Editor's comments from triage

12. Overall, the methods section could be more detailed, particularly in explaining how the literature was searched and screened (bearing in mind my background in systematic review, I tend to be quite exacting about this), the extraction of data, the classification of KE and KER strength, and synthesis of the literature to produce the weighted AOP network. [**Editor's note:** This is the "methodological gap" I referred to in my summary comments at the top of the report. There are additional comments on this in the next section as well.]
13. Structuring the methods in terms of eligibility criteria, search strings, screening method, data extraction, and network creation sections (including the classification of KE and KER strength) would help make explicit the steps from the raw literature to the synthesised AOP networks.

Reviewer 2

14. Lines 46-47 of pg3, please outline how generative AI tools were utilised to support the manual evaluation.

5. Are the methods detailed and clear, with sufficient raw data and code to provide for transparency and potential tests of reproducibility?

Editor's summary of reviewer comments and suggestions for responding

The reviewers have identified some important gaps in information about the methods being used to develop the AOP networks that should be filled. These suggest comprehensive revisions - the validity of the putative AOP networks is not at issue, but how they have actually been derived from the literature is not clear, so there is a considerable issue with transparency of approach here.

Reviewer comments

Editor's comments from triage

15. **For search and screening**, I would suggest the following:

- a. Using PRISMA-S. While appreciating this is not a systematic review, use of PRISMA-S will help the authors provide all the information a reader might expect in relation to reporting their search methodology.
- b. Adding complete search strings. Query terms alone are not sufficient for validating or reproducing the search.
- c. Making the eligibility criteria more explicit. Eligibility criteria for selection of studies for inclusion have not been explicitly stated (it seems to be related to a labelling process, but under what conditions an "include: yes" label is applied is not clear to me; there is no record of the reason why a study is excluded, although there is detailed numeric data on number of exclusions).
- d. Explaining the exclusion of non-open access articles. Exclusion of non open access articles seems to introduce a major limitation into the study, which is not clearly acknowledged in the discussion even though publication bias is

discussed. The authors only gesture at what publication bias is, offer no analysis of it, and overlook how including only open access articles could introduce publication bias. I would also expect the authors to have access to this literature through university subscriptions, so the reason for exclusion based on open access status is not clear to me.

- e. Providing more detail on the use of generative AI in the study. The authors mention the use of generative AI tools to evaluate articles, but it is not clear in what context or what for. Are the authors assessing the quality of articles, their eligibility, supporting data abstraction or network development, or what?

16. **For extraction of data**, I would suggest providing more detail. There is only a brief paragraph, in the screening section, about the collection of data that is relevant to the development of the AOP networks. Providing more detail about what data was collected and why (probably in the form of a data schema), and how data was collected (a human process? in duplicate? automated?) may be a solution.

17. **For synthesis**, I would suggest more detail about how the authors derived their results from the included literature. At the moment, there are gaps between the gathering of literature, the categorisation of KE and KE strength, and how this information is transformed into a network. The manuscript jumps from strength criteria straight into results, without describing the methods that were used to make strength judgements or to derive the networks from the literature.

- a. Some of this information is implicit in the strength criteria and narrative results, but it is not complete, and the specific processes by which the literature was interpreted into judgements of strength (e.g. who did this, how?) to develop the AOP networks is absent. How KEs and KERs were derived from the literature is also not clear (e.g. was it through an annotation or coding exercise, was it supported by AI or NLP tools?).
- b. It does not necessarily matter if the processes were subjective (e.g. expert judgement of the investigators) but they do need to be made explicit. The aggregation of the literature may also not be systematic (in that, relationships

may not have been systematically extracted), and this may be fine for a putative network [**Editor's note:** the peer-reviewers commented on this further, as hoped], but the methods still need to be made explicit.

Reviewer 1

18. It is unclear how the Boolean and categorical labels were used for screening and/or building the AOP network. [**Editor's note:** I think the issue might be that describing the labelling process is not the same thing as explaining the function that the labelling process performs.]
19. I am unfamiliar with the Sysrev software. Are there additional details about training the machine learning algorithm for inclusion prediction? The details provided seem scarce.
20. How was information extracted from the articles?
21. How were “key events” extracted from articles? My suspicion is that most articles did not specifically indicate what measurements were considered “key events”. Similarly, how was AOP relevance determined?
22. The meaning of the statement “Most were retrieved from PubMed, supplemented by reviews and Ontox project publications” is unclear to me.
23. How did you determine which measurements to include as Key events in the putative AOP network?
24. The authors provided a list of criteria for evaluating KE certainty and KER strength. Although this is quite different from the criteria recommended by the OECD for developing AOPs, it is acceptable for this putative network scoping study. However, the authors do not provide any details on how specific KEs and KERs were evaluated. Can the authors provide a table (perhaps in the supplemental information) with the details/evidence for how KE certainty and KER strength were determined? [**Editor's note:** In triage, I commented similarly, see next section.]

Reviewer 2

25. lines 56 of pg2 to 15 of pg3, The search terms used seem to be based on prior knowledge of what is important in neural tube closure. The search included a comprehensive set of keywords related to NTC anatomical structures (e.g., notochord, neural groove), metabolic pathways (e.g., folic acid cycle, one-carbon metabolism), cellular behaviors (e.g., neural crest cell migration, actin turnover), and signaling pathways (e.g., Shh, Wnt, RHOA). Please state how you decided to use these terms? Was it prior knowledge, extracted from a text book or relevant manuscripts?
26. line 14 of pg 3, for “ROS, SHH, BMP, FGF, WNT, TGF- β , CDH, RDH, FST, ZIC, RHOA” did you only search by abbreviation, or did you search the full terms too? Please be explicit.
27. lines 48-49 of pg3 refers to the SI. I could not access the SI to check these details.
28. Lines 53-54 of pg3, this sentence is not entirely clear? Could it be change to “Most were article describing original research (retrieved from PubMed), supplemented by reviews and Ontox project publications.
29. Lines 50-52 pg3, an explanation of how this information was then manipulated into aspects of an AOP would be useful. i.e. were cellular compartments and developmental timings were used to define the context of the AOPs? Signalling pathways, KEs and downstream effects were evaluated to develop the KEs and KERs? In other words it would be good to understand the process of how the AOPs were developed. It seems that this section ends and the next section jumps straight into an AOP was developed.
30. line 34-35 of pg4, how was this scoring category developed? Is it based on an AOP/MoA WoE assessment papers, the AOP developers handbook or your own criteria? Please elaborate. If you did not use the AOP developers handbook or a published method then it would be worth describing why not, and how your approach differs.

6. Are the authors' results clearly presented, and their findings and conclusions justified given their data and methodological processes?

Editor's summary of reviewer comments and suggestions for responding

There are important comments about how successful the authors' reliance on visualisation of data has been in getting the underlying data across, and some potentially helpful suggestions for tabulating the data and supporting it with simpler visualisations that may communicate more clearly to the reader the most salient parts of the AOP networks for each NTD mechanism. Substantial revisions relating to the use of figures seem necessary. There are also comments about the validity of choices of MIEs.

Reviewer comments

Editor's comments from triage

31. Please include the PRISMA figure directly in the manuscript, it is an important part of understanding the approach to the literature review.

32. The authors imply a manual search that supplements the PubMed search (final paragraph of section 2.2, "supplemented by reviews and ONTOX project publications") but this is not sufficiently transparently documented. These sources are not included in the PRISMA flow chart.

33. I feel there might be an insufficient amount of the kind of information that a reader might expect to see in the results of applying the method, that would demonstrate that the method has been successfully applied.
 - a. I think this would include a more direct connection between the literature that is the evidence for the KERs and KEs, and the judgements of strength. At the moment, the judgements of strength are only shown graphically, and the connected literature presented as citations within narrative text. I am not sure if the reader would be able to determine from this information what evidence informs each judgement (i.e. which included studies supporting the KE or KER), nor can they easily systematically validate the judgements made by the authors.

- b. One solution to this could be to present a table including all the KEs and KERs (there are a lot, but to generate the visualisation this table must effectively already exist?), with a statement of the judgement of strength for each KE or KER, the supporting studies that are the evidence for the judgement of strength, and a brief explanation of why the studies show the criteria for the judgement have been met. This would, I think, show that the visualisations and narrative are directly grounded in the literature, and make the whole process transparent.

34. I expect that addressing this comment will help make clear what methodological information needs to be provided to address the comments I made in section 2 above.

Reviewer 1

35. Results: I have several comments regarding the **figures**:

- a. Figure 2 was very low resolution and extremely difficult to read. I hope this is improved before publication.
- b. It was difficult to notice the difference between figures 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6. After a while, I realized that they are all the same network with slightly different shading. This also made it difficult to compare what was written in the text with figures. Here are some suggestions to improve this
 - i. Option 1: remove “unused” KEs from each subnetwork figure, so that each diagram is a unique network, with the full combined network shown only in a single figure
 - ii. Option 2: can you make the differences more obvious (e.g. stronger contrast in colours, or different border colours, ect...) and provide a description of these difference in the figure caption? [**Editor’s note**: There is a lot of data conveyed in the visualisation, and I am not sure the visualisation scheme is capable of conveying so much data - or even if a single visualisation scheme can realistically be expected to convey so much data to a reader - hence my suggestion of using the visualisations to complement rather than substitute for a data table. This reviewer has

also made some additional interesting suggestions - I look forward to seeing the authors' response.]

- iii. Option 3: combine into a single image, using colors/shapes to indicate the different subnetworks (maybe like a transit network diagram?):

Reviewer 2

39. General comment on figures – it is quite difficult to distinguish between figures 2-6. It looks like all the KEs are applicable to each and every pathway. The difference is the level of confidence associated with each AOP network, however it is difficult to distinguish between the confidences when looking at each AOP. Perhaps the strength and certainty image in figure 1 could be included in each figures 2-6. Additionally, ensuring that the text fits within each KE box would make the figures slightly more readable.
40. Due to the importance of MIEs with AOPs, not including the potential MIEs in the figures is disappointing, and the proposed MIEs for each section should be more prominent. A table of these MIEs would be useful and the table should contain one column for the MIE, one column for the KE(s) that they may feed into and a column to highlight the strength of each KER. If this is not clarified then I do not think the manuscript truly reflects an AOP network.
41. Typically AOPs are linear and do not contain feedback loops, I think the two multidirectional KERs within Figure 4 should be discussed in brief detail.
42. line 25 pg 7 – I do not think ‘altered dishevelled recruitment or stability’ should be classed as an MIE, as typically an MIE involved an interaction of a stressor with a biological entity, and I believe an interaction of a stressor and biological entity would have had to occur to drive the altered dishevelled recruitment. Please consider this and make appropriate changes or clarifications to this and other similar MIEs.
43. I feel like more effort could be put into linking the compounds to KEs... also there are only a few MIEs described in this section [Section 3.1], I don't feel like these would clutter the figure particularly so I would suggest adding these in or representing them in a table as suggested above.
44. I think not clarifying the MIEs is quite a gap in this research and I think without them, there may be limited practical use to these AOPs. If you disagree, please clarify this more in the introduction. (i.e. highlighting how AOPs without defined MIEs are useful for

risk assessments).

45. line 16-17 pg 8, talks about the causal role of a piece of evidence [Section 3.2]. It is useful evidence, but like all the evidence in this paper it is quite hard to evaluate/link to the relevant KER or KE. It would be some effort, but matching the evidence to the specific KERs would make it much clearer to the readers. This is not an essential change, but would clarify the research for readers.

46. Lines 47 pg8 to lines 6 of pg9 – the MIEs defined in this section are much clearer and obvious candidate MIEs when compared to the previous MIE section.

47. Section 3.3 possible MIEs

- a. Line 4 pg10 – I would not class reduced Grhl expression as an MIE. What interaction of a stressor and biological entity would lead to a decrease in Grhl expression?
- b. - the same stressors 2,4-D and caffeine are described here as other MIE sections. Is this because these compounds activate multiple MIEs related to NTDs, or the specific interactions are not particularly well supported/understood?
- c. Lines 57 pg9 to 17 pg 10, please consider adding some references to this section.
- d. Folate disruption is classed as possible MIEs? It is hard to see from the corresponding AOP figure which pathways relate to folate disruption, could this be clarified please? The table of putative MIEs and how they relate to KEs in the network would achieve this.
- e. Methotrexate and nicotine are also described.... Make it clear which bits of the described pathways you believe these chemicals to be perturbing and add citations for this

48. Section 3.4

- a. Lines 7-19 of pg 11 – Please review the putative MIEs and focus those which clearly define interactions of stressors with a biological entity. I do not regard “reduction in cellular signalling” or “impaired upstream GEF-mediated GTP loading” as MIEs
- b. [Regarding the sentence] “Exposures that perturb neural crest-associated migration and adhesion programs, including imidacloprid, glyphosate and tebuconazole can also plausibly impair coordinated tissue rearrangement at the fusion site.”. It would be good to understand what are the primary targets for these compounds and how these feed into the AOP.
- c. [In section 4] Line 7 of pg12 – please can you elaborate on what an “agent based model” is?

7. Comments on summary sections

Reviewer 1

49. **Title:** please change “AOP Network” to “Putative AOP Network”. This should also be done throughout the text.

50. **Abstract:** the abstract largely contained background information on AOPs and neural tube development. The abstract should be re-written to summarize the work conducted in this study. For example it should contain more information about the methods used and the resulting network and subnetworks.

Reviewer 2

51. This is a nicely written abstract. **[Editor’s note:** Fair enough! As for all revision suggestions, it is up to the authors to decide how to revise their manuscript, especially if reviewer comments are in conflict or if they seem unreasonable or unfeasible.]

52. On line 39 should it be “we present an AOP network for neural tube...” rather than “we present an AOP for neural tube....”?

8. Minor issues

Reviewer 2

53. Line 8 of pg2, there is an extra spacing in front of the comma “Protection Agency) , remain”
54. lines 53-54 on pg 2, there are a few instances where you refer to developing an AOP rather than an AOP network. I think all of these instances should state that you have developed a network of AOPs. i.e. please change this sentence to say “...establish a qualitative AOP network for NTDs...”
55. Consider changing the title of section 2.2 to “literature screening”?
56. Reference to figure 1 should be made somewhere in section 2.4, currently it is not referred to at all.
57. line 21-24 pg 7, “this AOP section initiate when a perturbation reduces non-canonical Wnt5a/Wnt11...” please review the wording of this sentence as it is difficult to follow.
58. Line 26 pg8, what is TOLOGRAM1?
59. Line 21 pg8 – what is DLHP? I do not think it has been previously defined.
60. Line 29 pg8 – I don’t think RA has been defined.
61. Lines 39-45 – where are the references?
62. Lines 47-7(pg9) – please add citations here, reciting the relevant ones used above.
63. Line 38 of pg 9 – I don’t think NNE has been defined
64. lines 51-52 of page 10 – I don’t quite understand the end of the following sentence, if possible please amend to make it clearer - “The role of Cdc42 is less clear: early defects occur, but mutants suggest filopodia may not be strictly required [32].

65. Line 36 of pg 11 – please clarify that the AOPs within the wiki are not complete e.g. “the draft linear AOPs currently listed in the AOP-wiki”

66. Line 14 of pg12 – change ‘contracting’ to ‘constructing’

The structure of this evaluation report is derived from the reviewer and author guidelines for Registered Reports (Chambers et al. 2023, <https://osf.io/pukzy>).